

Scanning electron microscopy observations of the flag leaf blade surface at the abaxial side of a dripping-wet mutant. Nipponbare (wild type) (a and b) dripping-wet leaf mutant (c and d). LP = large papillae, SP = small papillae, S = stomata, P = pili.

is one of the putative causes of wettability. To study the histological basis of leaf wettability, we observed the leaf surface of the newly obtained dripping-wet leaf mutant under a scanning electron microscope.

We observed that the dripping-wet leaf mutant was also an epicuticular waxless mutant. Large and small papillae, stomata, and pili on the mutant leaves were not so different from those on wild types (see figures 1a, 1c). However, the mutant leaf had a plain surface with epicuticular wax less developed than that found in wild types (see figure 1b, 1d). We also investigated the inheritance of epicuticular wax and dripping-wet leaf traits in crosses of mutant type/wild type and wild type/mutant type. The F_1 plants in both crosses were wild types. In the F_2 of both crosses, dripping-wet leaf plants always had the epicuticular waxless trait. The segregation ratio of the wild type to mutant type (dripping-wet leaf and epicuticular waxless) fitted to a 3-1 ratio

in both crosses, indicating that the dripping-wet leaf trait was caused by reduced leaf epicuticular wax.

Many mutants with less epicuticular wax accumulation were already obtained in *Arabidopsis*, barley, and wheat (Lemieux et al 1994). Reduced wax on the leaf surface altered the reflection of light, which allowed isolation of the mutants through visual inspection. These mutants were designated as glossy or nonglaucous mutants. The dripping-wet leaf mutant of rice might be one of these mutants with reduced epicuticular wax.

Cited references

- Lemieux B, Koornneef M, Feldmann KA. 1994. Epicuticular wax and eceriferum mutants. In: Meyerowitz and Somerville, editors. *Arabidopsis*. New York: Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press. p 1031 - 1047.
- Sato H, Iwata N, Omura T. 1983. Gene analysis of some dripping-wet leaf mutants in rice. *Jpn. J. Breed.* 33 (Suppl. 2): 243-243. ■

Embryonic cell suspensions established from a high-protein purple black rice

Huihua Fu, Tingliang Tian, Biology Department, Central China Normal University, Wuhan 430070, China; and Yingguo Zhu, Biology Department, Wuhan University, Wuhan 430072, China

Establishing embryonic cell suspensions is important in regenerating plants from rice protoplasts. We studied the effects of explants, media, hormones, and culture suspension procedures on callus induction and cell suspension of indica variety HuaHei 01, a new high-protein purple black rice derived from progenies of Hua 03/Hong Jing 501.

Effects of explants. We cultured explants from young panicles (1-10 mm), anther at mid-uninucleate stage, and mature seeds on Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium supplemented with $2 \text{ mg } 2,4\text{-D L}^{-1} + 0.2 \text{ mg Kin L}^{-1}$. The lowest callus induction (0.4%) was obtained from anthers. Young panicles had high callus induction (24.6%), as did mature seeds (21.3%). Calli from anthers and mature seed were compact, globular, and yellow, and could be used to establish embryonic cell suspensions. Calli from young panicles were scattered and pale yellow.

Effects of media and hormone ratios. We chose MS, N6, and GM supplemented with different ratios of hormones for incubating explants. AA, N6, and MS with $2 \text{ mg } 2,4\text{-D L}^{-1} + 0.2 \text{ mg Kin L}^{-1}$ was used for the liquid suspension culture. Although the calli induction rate on N6, MS, and GM media did not significantly differ, the quality of calli induced on the various media did. Most of the calli induced on N6 were yellow, compact, and globular, and grew rapidly; those induced on MS and GM grew slowly. Calli in the AA liquid medium remained yellow, while those in the N6 and MS media turned brown in the first month of suspension.

Hormones significantly affected induction frequency and callus quality. Time required for callus induction was shortened, and some calli induced were pale yellow with root hairs when 4 mg NAA L^{-1} , $1 \text{ mg } 2,4\text{-D L}^{-1}$, and $0.2 \text{ mg Kin L}^{-1}$ were supplemented. However, induction

Effects of hormones on callus induction from mature seeds of rice.^a

Hormone (mg L ⁻¹)	Callus Induction frequency (%)	Callus characteristics
NAA (4) + 2,4-D (1) + kinetin (0.2)	20.8	Pale yellow; some calli with root hairs
2,4-D (2) + kinetin (0.2)	24.2	Globular, compact, and yellow

^aBasic medium used was Murashige and Skoog (MS).

frequency was slightly higher and calli were fresh yellow, compact, and globular when supplemented with 2 mg 2,4-D L⁻¹ and 0.2 mg Kin L⁻¹ (see table).

Effect of culturing procedures. When calli reached 1-2 mm in diameter, half were transferred into AA, MS, and N6 liquid media supplemented with 2 mg 2,4-D L⁻¹ and 0.2 mg Kin L⁻¹ and shaken at 120 rpm.

The other half was subcultured onto the same induction medium with 500 mg proline L⁻¹ for 10 d to 6 mo (subcultured once a month) and then transferred into liquid suspension culture. Calli turned brown and died in 3-4 d in liquid culture with immediate transfer or subculture for less than 1 mo. On the other hand, calli could propagate quickly when transferred

into liquid media after subculture on solid induction media for 1 mo or longer. At the start of suspension culture, the calli were subcultured every 3 d by replacing all original medium with the same fresh medium. After 4 wk, the aggregates grew well, and cultures were subcultured every 6 d by replacing two-thirds of the original medium with the same fresh medium. Subsequently, the well-grown cultures released many miniclusters into the liquid medium. Thus, through about 3 mo of suspension culture, we obtained embryogenic cell suspensions composed mainly of cell aggregates consisting of 10-60 cells with fresh yellow color and dense cytoplasm. ■

Factors affecting pollen embryogenesis of rice anther culture

J. K. Sohn, Agronomy Department, Kyungpook National University, Taegu, Republic of Korea (ROK); G. H. Yi, B. G. Oh, National Youngnam Agricultural Experiment Station, 1085, Milyang, ROK; S. J. Yang, IRR: and T. S. Kwak, Agronomy Department, Sangi University, Weonju, ROK

Anther culture techniques as a means of breeding are considered effective and time-saving methods for obtaining pure linea in rice and for other major crop improvement.

Pollen embryogenesis is believed to provide new prospects for anther culture because of its stability and enhanced recovery of regenerants.

We occasionally observed pollen embryogenesis during rice anther culture in many cultivars and F₁ plants in our laboratory. Growth regulators, water stress, and media composition affect the induction rate of pollen embryogenesis (Torrizo and Zapata 1986).

Abscisic acid (ABA) in the callus formation medium was most effective for pollen embryogenesis of rice; callus formation from the anthers plated did not increase significantly. However, embryo formations were markedly increased.

Table 1. Effects of abscisic acid (ABA) on embryo and callus formation in rice anther culture.

ABA (mg L ⁻¹)	Responding anthers (%)	Calli formed (%)	Embryos formed (%)
0	19.7 ± 2.3 ^a	8.4 ± 1.1	1.6 ± 0.4
0.5	28.8 ± 2.2	9.1 ± 1.1	10.8 ± 1.2
1.0	19.7 ± 2.1	7.2 ± 1.2	7.2 ± 0.8
5.0	18.1 ± 1.8	6.6 ± 1.0	8.8 ± 0.9
10.0	15.1 ± 1.6	7.3 ± 0.9	5.5 ± 0.9
20.0	7.8 ± 1.4	2.9 ± 0.7	3.2 ± 0.5

^aMean ± SE.

Table 2. Effects of growth regulators on germination of pollen embryos in rice anther culture.

Growth regulators (mg L ⁻¹)			Plants (%)	
Zeatin	IAA ^a	Kinetin	Green	Albino
1	0	0	6.1 ± 2.0 ^b	5.0 ± 5.0
5	0	0	13.9 ± 3.9	5.0 ± 5.0
1	0.2	0	8.6 ± 1.8	2.0 ± 2.0
5	0.2	0	9.8 ± 0.2	0
0	0.5	2	26.7 ± 1.9	0
0	0	0	8.0 ± 1.0	8.0 ± 5.8

^aIAA = indole acetic acid. ^bMean ± SE.

Maximum frequency (10.8%) of embryo formation was obtained at 0.5 ppm ABA (Table 1). Also, ABA treatment during the cold pretreatment period (15 °C, 15 d) showed the same tendency as that under in vitro condition.

We tested several combinations of plant growth regulators for germinating pollen embryos. The combination of 0.5 ppm

indole acetic acid and 2.0 ppm kinetin was suitable for germinating embryos (Table 2).

The results indicate that ABA is important in plant regeneration and embryo formation in rice anther culture.

Cited reference

Torrizo LB, Zapata FJ. 1986. Anther culture of rice. IV. The effect of abscisic acid on plant regeneration. *Plant Cell Rep.* 5:136-139. ■